

A STOCHASTIC APPROACH TO MODEL VOID FORMATION DURING OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE PREPREG CONSOLIDATION

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ABSTRACT

Material variability is always present in prepreg materials. Accompanied by fluctuations in process parameters, handling and environmental conditions, these inherent uncertainties can lead to significant variations in void content within the final part. This is especially critical for processing thermoset Out-of-Autoclave (OoA) prepregs since the safeguard provided by high autoclave pressure no longer exists. For a more realistic simulation of void formation during OoA processing, contingencies in input parameters have to be considered. Stochastic models are suitable to account for random input factors in order to quantify process output variations. This is a prerequisite to reduce the risk of unserviceable quality of parts to a minimum. The following study attempts to allocate different input variabilities to three types of voids in OoA prepregs and highlights stochastic approaches to model each of them individually.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

The increasing demand for composite materials as well as the need for sustainability promoted the replacement of pressurized autoclaves by conventional ovens for the consolidation of prepreg material. The lack of pressure makes part fabrication vulnerable to voids formation. Gas cannot be dissolved in the resin, as performed during autoclave processing where the external pressure can reach up to 8 bar. Thermoset Out-of-Autoclave (OoA) prepregs have been designed to counteract quality degradation when parts are consolidated in a vacuum bag-only.. These prepreg materials are initially only partly impregnated and consist of both dry and resin rich areas. Dry regions are interconnected and centrally located within the layer to serve as evacuation channels for volatiles entrapped within the laminate. Though beneficial for gas evacuation, evacuation channels bear the risk of staying dry if not fully impregnated by the resin before gelation. Accordingly, voids within OoA laminates can be defined as hollow spaces that enclose vacuum, air or other volatiles. Mechanical properties can be significantly reduced by voids. Thus, producing void free OoA parts is desirable but challenging due to limited consolidation pressure. This turns void formation phenomena into a major concern in OoA production. Optimal utilization of evacuation pathways requires a careful selection and control of material properties and manufacturing parameters based on a thorough understanding of process phenomena.

In production, the exact outcome of a process and therewith the final part quality underlies a wide range of uncertainties. This can result in a high percentage of rejects associated with significant costs and environmental consequences. OoA prepregs are machine-made, however, material uncertainties are always present. Representing the process by a scientific model cannot be strictly limited to one

single input parameter but has to take multiple input values into account. This results in a variety of process outputs with an according probability.

To make sophisticated decisions, such as the selection of optimal process variables, it is important to understand the relationship between input and output parameters. A stochastic representation of the initial material constitution and processing parameters is therefore indispensable for a reliable determination of the material properties as to void content at the end of the consolidation process.

1.2 Background

Several recent studies have evaluated the influence of material and process parameters on OoA prepreg void formation experimentally. Fibre bed architecture, resin viscosity (cure cycle and out-time) and pressure/air evacuation parameters were shown to influence void formation [1, 2, 3]. The effect of moisture content on void formation was examined by [4], concluding that the void volume fraction in OoA processing increases exponentially as a function of moisture content. Above mentioned studies demonstrated the sensitivity of OoA processing techniques to changes in environmental conditions, manufacturing parameters and material properties. This motivates the importance of understanding the effect of uncertainties on OoA consolidation phenomena.

A general overview of material and processing variability in composite structures was given in [5], concluding that optimal process designs can only be achieved through stochastic simulation tools. The importance of stochastic simulation methodologies was attached to various processing steps: variations in fibre volume fraction and effect on permeability were analysed statistically by [6] and integrated in an infiltration model by [7, 8].

Nevertheless, an integrated process model to describe void formation in OoA prepregs is missing in literature and mathematical modelling of prepreg processing has mainly focused on deterministic formulations throughout the last decades. This omits the role of uncertainties and limits their predictive ability. More rigorous formulations need to be developed that account for these uncertainties, quantify their effect on the final void content and assess the reliability.

1.2 Objective

This study aims to point out possible applications of mathematical models available in stochastics that are suitable for the description of random effects in OoA prepreg material. Focus of this work will be the identification of random parameters and as well as their mathematical realization rather than the precise implementation and discussion of results. The intention is to generate an increased awareness of the variability in the origin of voids present in OoA prepregs. The existent three different types of voids are subsequently used as an example to explain different stochastic methods. Characterization methods to calibrate the models accordingly are briefly mentioned, too.

2 VOID CLASSIFICATION IN OOA PREPREGS

As mentioned beforehand, voids within OoA laminates can be defined as hollow spaces that enclose vacuum, air or other volatiles. Various void generation and void dissipation mechanisms determine void formation during processing in consequence of the OoA material constitution, processing and lay-up. Several sources can be attributed to void generation: air entrapped between plies during lay-up, volatiles released during cure, diffusion and vaporization of moisture dissolved in the resin and incomplete impregnation of initially dry areas within the prepreg. Autoclave pressures, effectively forcing gases to remain in solution to prevent void formation, are not available in OoA processing. This leaves vacuum evacuation of entrapped gasses and hydrostatic resin pressure as the only dissipation mechanisms for voids [9].

According to [10], voids present in OoA prepregs after processing can be classified into three different types based on their origin: inter-ply voids, resin voids and intra-ply (fibre tow) voids. A more detailed description of each type can be found in the according section below. Sources and dominant dissipation mechanism will be described from a stochastic point of view, motivating the introduction of stochastic approaches suitable for the according type of void formation.

3 RESIN VOIDS

Compared to conventional prepregs, OoA prepregs are modified in their resin rheology, using addition-cured thermoset resins to avoid off-gassing during cure [11]. Accordingly, resin voids can primarily be attributed to moisture dissolved in the resin. Moisture particles can nucleate and form voids. Again, due to the relatively small resin pressure in OoA processes, a re-dissolution of moisture bubbles may not occur.

3.1 Bubble Growth Phenomena

Void growth or dissolution is determined by moisture diffusion through the liquid resin as well as pressure and temperature conditions. The diffusive flux of water molecules across the bubble-resin interface depends on the direction of the moisture concentration gradient between bubble and surrounding resin. Higher temperatures facilitate the diffusion of moisture and accelerate the process of void growth with increasing temperature. If the internal pressure P_{gas} in a bubble of radius R exceeds the hydrostatic pressure in the surrounding resin P_{resin} plus surface tension γ , the bubble will expand until the pressure is balanced again, according to Eq. 1.

$$P_{gas} = P_{resin} + \frac{2 \cdot \gamma}{R} \quad (1)$$

Voids containing pure air will collapse under the resin pressure, while void growth is promoted when voids contain a water air mixture, due to the exponential increase of water vapor pressure with temperature [4]. Accordingly, both, changes in temperature and pressure conditions directly disturb the equilibrium of bubble gas and resin pressure and induce a change in void size during processing until higher viscosity hinders further bubble growth.

3.2 Material Uncertainty and Background

The negative effect of increased relative humidity on void content in OoA prepregs was proven experimentally by [4, 12, 13, 14, 15]. The theory of void growth in liquid media has been studied by many researchers in various fields [16, 17, 18]. The application to bubble growth in (autoclave) prepreg material was first conducted by Kardos et al [13], followed by Wood and Bader [19] and Ledru [20] in various levels of detail.

Grunenfelder transferred the model developed by Kardos to OoA processing [4]. Most before mentioned models describe the change in size of one bubble assuming a distinct initial size. Other researcher have used the classical nucleation theory to model the moisture induced formation of a new phase (void) within the resin [16, 21]. These models describe water vapor nuclei that form at certain degrees of supersaturation, whereas air nuclei, existing due to the entrapment of air [13], are not considered. Furthermore, homogeneous nucleation theory was used in all models, assuming that no impurities exist in the resin system. Kweeder et al. [22] proposes that a pre-existing population of microvoids within the polymer serves as the precursor for void growth.

3.3 Stochastic Approach

Nucleation theory is closely related to probability theory, which motivates the application of stochastic models to determine the likelihood of void content due to bubble growth. Amon applies a constant, but random number of bubbles per unit mass of polymer with a distinct initial radius [23]. Stochastic point processes could be the tool of choice to determine the number of voids per unit volume as well as the initial bubble size, as indicated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Bubble distribution in a liquid (left) and a marked point process generated in Matlab (right)

Poisson point processes Π_λ are determined by the intensity function $\lambda > 0$, which refers to the number of points per unit area. Π_λ is called a homogeneous Poisson process if λ is constant, otherwise it is said to be inhomogeneous. The determination of λ can be achieved experimentally by evaluating the amount of bubbles in a distinct volume after cure and concluding on the initial distribution in reversed order. [21] developed a 1D model taking into account the desorption of volatiles during the heating process. Similar assumptions can be considered by an inhomogeneous Poisson process. For the size of the initial bubble, a Gaussian distribution can be used. The dissolution of bubbles, that is, the Ostwald ripening, occurs when the bubble radius is smaller than the critical radius. Therefore, a minimum initial bubble radius is given by the critical size, while the maximum size is not clearly limited, due to the possibility of entrapped air serving as the initial bubble.

Given the initial distribution and size of voids, bubble growth during cure is evaluated through modelling, as suggested by [13, 20, etc.]. To quantify the effect of uncertainty in initial bubble size and location on final resin void content, Monte Carlo Simulation can be used.

It should be noted that for example [13] claims that for sufficiently high water contents void growth will occur and the problem of transporting the voids out of the laminate is extremely important. This is supported by experimental studies in [1]. Modelling bubble motion, especially through the tortuosity of fibres, is very computationally intensive.

4 INTRA-PLY VOIDS

To counteract quality degradation due to a lack of consolidation pressure, OoA preregs have a special purpose design, consisting of dry and resin rich areas. Dry areas are permeable and establish channels to allow for gas evacuation and accordingly void dissipation. After an initial vacuum hold time, heat is applied and resin supplied by resin rich areas infiltrates the dry microstructure. Full prepreg impregnation is desired before gelation, but concurrently evacuation channels have to stay permeable sufficiently long to ensure that no gas remains in the laminate. Areas within the fibre tow remaining unimpregnated throughout the manufacturing process become voids in the final part. They are referred to as intra-ply voids.

4.1 Material Uncertainty

In unidirectional preregs, unimpregnated areas are considered to form a permeable layer in between layers of resin rich areas. The initial degree of impregnation (*IDOI*) indicates the percentage of interstitial volume of the fibre bed filled with resin. This is the fraction of the resin volume V_r and the volume of impregnated fibres V_{if} within a selected composite's volume V_c .

$$IDOI = \frac{V_r + V_{if}}{V_c} \quad (2)$$

In this study the *IDOI* was determined by a 3D computer tomographic image of the prepreg cross-section (Fig. 2 (a)). The boundary between wet and dry areas, i.e. the flow front, was irregularly distributed and accordingly the *IDOI*. In order to quantify the variability of the *IDOI*, the *IDOI* was evaluated for every pixel column in thickness direction. The according 2D colour plot is shown in Fig. 2 (b).

Figure 2: (a) Cross-section of a UD OoA prepreg and (b) distribution of the *IDOI* in a ply [24].

A higher local *IDOI* implies a smaller distance for the resin to flow, which might close evacuation channels at an early stage. This cannot be captured by a model when assuming a constant level of impregnation. Therefore, a simulation of OoA processing can be significantly improved by taking into consideration the materials variability.

4.2 Stochastic Approach

Various flow and compaction models are available in the literature which simulate resin flow through a porous medium (fibre bed) using Darcy's law, accounting for initially dry areas within the prepreg ply [2, 25]. However, void formation due to imperfect impregnation was not incorporated. This motivated modelling the initial resin distribution stochastically. The *IDOI* was chosen to be represented as a specially varying property which can subsequently be used as the input for a (2D) consolidation model. One approach is to use a random field $IDOI(x, \omega)$ depending on the stochastic variable ω and the space variable x . The Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process was chosen to represent this field, which is a stationary Gaussian process with constant mean value and a covariance function represented by a one parameter function $C_{IDOI}(\Delta x)$. Two flow fronts determined by samples of the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process are depicted in red and blue, respectively, in Fig. 3. The characteristic parameters of the process can be determined by CT images.

Figure 3: Two samples of the Ornstein Uhlenbeck Process (red, blue) used to represent the initial material constitution.

There are two approaches to quantify the effect of uncertainty through stochastic simulation: intrusive and non-intrusive methods. Intrusive techniques require a modification of the deterministic solvers. In contrast non-intrusive methods can be directly applied to available (deterministic) models [5]. The best known non-intrusive approach is the Monte Carlo method. The main drawback is the number of simulations required. A different approach to obtain information about the uncertainty propagation and therefore the reliability of the solution is to approximate the model's random output by a polynomial chaos expansion (PCE). PCE forms the basis for various types of collocation methods depending on the techniques for choosing the collocation points. Thereby, the probabilistic space is discretized to enable numerical calculation. Not every PCE is non-intrusive. A non-intrusive approach, where the coefficients are obtained using Gauss quadrature, is the Probabilistic Collocation Method (PCM). In [26] it was shown that the PCM can deliver similar results to the computationally expensive Monte Carlo simulations. Statistical moments and probability density functions can be calculated directly from the coefficients of the polynomial chaos expansion.

Thus, the model accounts for locally specific resin conditions, determining the flow behaviour across the laminate and finally the formation of fibre tow voids. There are multiple sources of input uncertainties leading to variations in flow behaviour and accordingly to potential void formation, namely fibre volume fraction, cure and edge effects among others. The above suggested model for uncertainty consideration in intra-ply voids can be applied to any other uncertainty parameter.

5 INTER-PLY VOIDS

Entrapment of air between plies is not surprising, given the multiple sources of uncertainty along the process chain: high variability in resin distribution due to manufacturing techniques as well as transport and storage incidents may affect the ply surface before final usage. Initial material condition as well as handling, temperature and contamination during lay-up have an important effect on air entrapment and may lead to detrimental voids after cure. The interaction of various properties may influence the amount of entrapped air as well as location and pattern during processing. Surface waviness may determine areas that are more likely to be in contact to adjacent plies, depending on pressure conditions. The surface roughness of a prepreg is an important parameter for both the amount of entrapped air as well as its removal [27]. According to [28] surface roughness has an enormous influence on many physical phenomena such as small scale contact mechanics, sealing, tack and friction. In turn, surface roughness can also generate interconnected pathways for air evacuation, before they might collapse and become disconnected during vacuum hold. But the inter-ply zone may not be the only evacuation possibility. If the resin distribution, as depicted in Fig. 2 allows for it, air will flow from the inter-ply zone into the intermediate, dry layer. Subsequently, air can either be removed by the evacuation channels, remain in the intermediate layer or flow in thickness direction.

Above mentioned sources of uncertainty suggest that stochastic models are the right tool of choice for modelling the entrapment of air during lay-up of unidirectional OoA prepregs. Nevertheless, little is known for air evacuation phenomena of inter-ply voids in unidirectional material. Literature lacks both, an experimental approach to identify the evacuation mechanisms that take effect on air entrapped between plies as well as according models. Therefore, this area demands a rather fundamental research.

Woven composites were analyzed in [1], concluding that inter-ply voids initially represent the greatest fraction of void content. These voids can mostly decrease to zero during processing, which can be attributed to air evacuation through gaps created by the interlaced structure. The same phenomena cannot be transferred to unidirectional prepregs without further ado, due to smoother surfaces compared to woven prepreg, as well as less air permeability in thickness direction [29].

6 CONCLUSIONS

Out-of-Autoclave prepregs, or prepreg materials in general, are random heterogeneous materials where uncertainties arise from the stochastic variability of their initial properties. Adding variability in handling, storage and processing can lower the informative value of deterministic process models even more and requests stochastic approaches. This study introduced stochastic methods that permit a consideration of variations within the prepreg material in order to quantify their effect on the laminate's final void content after processing. The authors are aware of the fact, that not all of the uncertainties which can arise during OoA manufacturing are addressed within this work. This work was rather intended to give an overview of potential mathematical methods that can be used to model material variability in OoA materials.

Finally, the models provide a basis for adding further parameter uncertainties, such as fibre volume fraction or curing variations as to out-time or inhomogeneous temperature distribution.

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